

MCAA feedback and policy position

April 9th, 2021

MCAA feedback to the Commission's roadmap for the Communication on the Global Approach to Research, Innovation, Education and Youth

Background

The Covid-19 pandemic has resulted in an unprecedented crisis in modern history with severe consequences for society. However, the EU has managed to reach a vital consent in the Next Generation recovery fund and now seeks for an agreement of the new EU's global approach to research, innovation, education and young people. The EU Next Generation fund is a great opportunity for all EU countries to substantially invest in their Research, Innovation, Education and Youth modernisation programmes and as such to strengthen the EU's research and innovation capacity. The roadmap presents a strong and urgent case to strengthen multilateralism and cooperation with like-minded countries to tackle global challenges in support of the EU's strategic priorities.

The Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA), a global network representing over 17,000 fellows and alumni of the European Union's most prestigious and competitive programme for the development of researchers' careers, welcomes the upcoming Communication of the European Commission and hereby expresses its feedback and policy position.

Summary

The MCAA recommends that the new Communication, and strategy it will set out, is approached as an opportunity:

1. To address discrepancies in R&I and HE development among EU countries as a prerequisite to engage in international collaborations with a research capacity that is strong at its base.
2. To continue to mobilize research talent so that the EU is an effective player in the global scene, through attractive working environments and career prospects for researchers.

3. To establish much needed multilateral collaborations to make progress towards the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and do so in the spirit of the EU's responsible research and innovation (RRI) approach.
4. To promote global values and principles, including academic freedom.
5. To promote European principles for open science and researcher wellbeing.

The MCAA recommends that the new Communication, and strategy it will set out, considers the following opportunities:

Addressing discrepancies in R&I and HE development among EU countries

The EU should ensure that its research capacity is strong at its base with quality education and care for future generations across all countries in the Union, through addressing discrepancies among EU countries. This will be a prerequisite to engage in international collaborations as a strong player. Since some EU countries have been facing challenges in conducting reforms and have not yet reached wide stakeholder support, it is essential that the European Commission reinforces the initiatives for reform and prevents any threat of not implementing them, despite proclaimed R&I national strategies and action plans. Careful monitoring of the Next Generation money allocation for Research, Innovation, Education and Youth recovery programmes, the persistent promotion of ethical principles and the EU 2019 whistleblower Directive aims are welcome measures in the prevention of misconduct in this regard.

Continuing to mobilize research talent to ensure the EU's role in the global scene

Welcome steps to achieve this include the strengthening of the ERA and 3% GDP investment target. However, more needs to be done to retain research talent in research careers (in Europe), and based on the current engagement of the research community in debates - on the precarity of researcher careers, the appropriateness of assessment systems, the struggles to make progress on inclusion and diversity as well as eradicate misconduct, both towards other researchers and towards the scientific record - the quality of work environments will be an important factor in this retention. Additional efforts are needed to reform research assessment and research careers (in Europe) to make research careers more sustainable and attractive. This should include (but be not restricted to) enabling researchers to focus on impact for society rather than journal impact factors as well as incentivising professional career development that leaves open a range of career options inside or outside academia where researchers can use their professional skills for the benefit of society.

Establishing multilateral collaborations in the spirit of the EU's RRI approach

The urgency of addressing global challenges requires the EU to focus on its contribution to achieving a sustainable future but equally to recognise that progress for the benefit of the global society will require innovations that are and will be researched in Europe to be implemented elsewhere in the world. Responsible research and innovation implies that key stakeholders are included in the research process from design to outputs, and in this context, this means including researchers as well as other relevant societal actors (citizens, governments, policy makers, businesses, third sector organisations, etc.) from those countries that will see the implementation of European innovations as true partners, while recognising that implementation will not just impact on citizens in those collaborating countries, but on the global population as a whole, including all European citizens.

Promotion of global values and principles, including academic freedom

The EU should ensure the full promotion of the universal and global values and principles as laid down in the [Universal Declaration of Human Rights](#), the [Magna Charta Universitatum](#) and the [Lima Declaration on Academic Freedom and Autonomy](#). The European Union should in first instance ensure that all its member states sign and live the [Bonn Declaration on Freedom of Scientific Research](#). In the spirit of these principles, we urge the EU to achieve the right balance when using its 'as open as possible and as closed as necessary' approach, with concerns that recent decisions are leaning unnecessarily to the 'closed' end of this dichotomy. If the EU is to achieve its ambitions to considerably contribute to tackling global challenges, it will need to rely on a range of partnerships with trustworthy partners. While efforts are needed to build additional multilateral relationships, continuing long-established relationships with strong R&I partners will be as important to succeed.

Promotion of European principles for open science and researcher wellbeing

Open science - While this will in first instance require Member States to further embrace open science principles, the EU is in an excellent position to enhance global uptake of open science practices and establish open science as a common goal. The pandemic has exemplified the need for openness and transparency, and access to data. There might not be a more significant time to further promote the need for and value of open science. As the EU is developing the European Open Science Cloud and will in due course be able to share benefits and learnings from this initiative, it is in a great position to not only share values and principles but also best practices on data sharing and data governance.

Researcher wellbeing - A great contribution in establishing the EU's leadership in R&I and HE is the promotion of well-being and mental health within research environments. The forthcoming Manifesto on Researcher Mental Health is the world's first public declaration on this relevant issue, funded by the EU's COST Action [Researcher Mental Health \(ReMO\)](#) and involved the participation of several MCAA members. It is expected that the Manifesto's guidelines can substantially contribute to the EU's efforts in addressing challenges around mental health and wellbeing and will result in a position to share guidelines but also to take a lead role in establishing future norms.

Signed by the MCAA Board on April 9th 2021.

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